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13.00.05	19.00.00	11.00.00

No5/2025

M AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogik, psixometodologik va tabiiy fanlarga
ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 438 sahifa,
14-may, 2025-yil.

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Asos: OAK Pedagogik texnologiyalar va psixologik tadqiqotlar bo’yicha ekspert kengashi tavsiyasi (29-10-2024-y.; №10); OAK Tartib-qoida komissiyasi qarori (30-10-2024-y., №10/24); OAK Rayosatining qarori (31-10-2024-y., №363/5).

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.06.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan №C-5669245
reyestr raqami tartibi bo’yicha
ro’yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310

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THE ROLE OF ENGLISH AS A TOOL FOR CULTURAL DIPLOMACY IN POST-SOVIET UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This study explores the role of English in Uzbekistan as a tool of cultural diplomacy during the post-Soviet period. Following independence, Uzbekistan adopted English as a strategic resource to shape its image on the international stage and to foster global integration. Using a qualitative research approach, the study analyzed documents from the Ministry of Education of Uzbekistan, reports from international organizations, and content from media and social networks. The findings reveal that English serves as a significant bridge in Uzbekistan's educational system, international cooperation, and cultural engagement, contributing to the enhancement of the country's global image. However, the growing presence of English also calls for a careful balance between promoting national identity and preserving local languages. The results of this study offer practical guidance for developing Uzbekistan's language policy and cultural diplomacy strategies. Moreover, they provide a basis for comparative analysis for other post-Soviet states. The study underscores the strategic importance of English in strengthening Uzbekistan's global position and presents recommendations for future policy reforms.

Key words: English, cultural diplomacy, Uzbekistan, post-Soviet, soft power, language policy, global integration, national identity, educational reform, international cooperation.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur tadqiqotda ingliz tilining O'zbekistonda post-Sovet davrida madaniy diplomatiya vositasi sifatidagi o'rni tahlil qilingan. Mustaqillikdan so'ng O'zbekiston ingliz tilini xalqaro maydondagi imijini shakllantirish va global integratsiyani kuchaytirishning strategik resursi sifatida qabul qildi. Tadqiqotda sifatli (kvalitativ) yondashuv asosida O'zbekiston Ta'lim vazirligi hujjatlari, xalqaro tashkilotlar hisobotlari, ommaviy axborot vositalari va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi kontentlar tahlil qilindi.

Natijalar ingliz tilining O'zbekistonning ta'lim tizimi, xalqaro hamkorlik va madaniy faoliyatida muhim ko'prik vazifasini bajarayotganini va mamlakatning global imijini mustahkamlashga xizmat qilayotganini ko'rsatdi. Shu bilan birga, ingliz tilining kengayib borishi milliy identitet va mahalliy tillarni saqlash masalalarida muvozanatni ta'minlashni talab etadi.

Tadqiqot natijalari O'zbekistonning til siyosati va madaniy diplomatiya strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda amaliy qo'llanma bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin, shuningdek, boshqa post-Sovet davlatlar uchun taqqoslama tahlilga asos bo'la oladi. Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tilining O'zbekistonning global maydondagi pozitsiyasini mustahkamlashdagi strategik ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi hamda kelajakdagi islohotlar bo'yicha tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tili, madaniy diplomatiya, O'zbekiston, post-Sovet, yumshoq kuch, til siyosati, global integratsiya, milliy identitet, ta'lim islohoti, xalqaro hamkorlik.

Аннотация: Данное исследование посвящено изучению роли английского языка в Узбекистане как инструмента культурной дипломатии в постсоветский период. После обретения независимости Узбекистан рассматривал английский язык как стратегический ресурс для формирования своего имиджа на международной арене и укрепления глобальной интеграции. В рамках качественного подхода были проанализированы документы Министерства образования Узбекистана, отчёты международных организаций, а также материалы СМИ и социальных сетей.

Результаты показали, что английский язык играет важную роль в образовательной системе, международном сотрудничестве и культурной деятельности, способствуя укреплению глобального имиджа Узбекистана. Вместе с тем расширение использования английского языка требует соблюдения баланса между национальной идентичностью и сохранением местных языков.

Полученные результаты могут служить практическим ориентиром при разработке языковой политики и стратегий культурной дипломатии Узбекистана, а также стать основой для сравнительного анализа среди других постсоветских государств. Исследование подчеркивает стратегическую значимость английского языка в укреплении позиции Узбекистана на мировой арене и предлагает рекомендации для будущих реформ.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, культурная дипломатия, Узбекистан, постсоветское пространство, мягкая сила, языковая политика, глобальная интеграция, национальная идентичность, образовательная реформа, международное сотрудничество.

INTRODUCTION

After the breakup of the Soviet Union in 1991, Uzbekistan set out to find its place in the international community as an independent state. This period marked significant changes for the country not only in terms of economic and political reforms but also in the formation of its image on a global scale. Following the declaration of independence (August 31, 1991), Uzbekistan sought to strengthen its image by promoting its rich historical and cultural heritage, particularly cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva along the Great Silk Road, on the international stage (Adams, 2010). In this process, cultural diplomacy and the development of a soft power strategy through the global promotion of the country's cultural values, art, and language have become key objectives. Uzbekistan actively engages in the preservation and promotion of its cultural heritage in cooperation with international organizations such as the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2023). At the same time, the country's global integration through education, tourism, and international exchange programs is accelerating, which further emphasizes the growing importance of the English language in cultural diplomacy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Uzbekistan's presence in the international arena has significantly expanded in recent years. Since 2017, the country has adopted an "open policy" strategy, increasing its engagement in foreign investment, tourism development, and international education programs (Khalid, 2021). As part of these strategies, English has become crucial as a global means of communication, not only expanding economic opportunities but also serving as a bridge for sharing Uzbekistan's cultural and social values with the international community.

The concept of cultural diplomacy refers to the use of cultural exchange, education, and the arts to foster mutual understanding among nations. Joseph Nye's soft power concept emphasizes that cultural diplomacy enhances a nation's international standing by presenting its values and culture in a way that is attractive to others (Nye, 2008). For developing countries such as Uzbekistan, cultural diplomacy serves as a key instrument for promoting international cooperation, attracting foreign investors and tourists, and participating in global educational systems. English plays a central role in this process, facilitating cultural and social interaction as a medium of global communication. For instance, English is the primary language used in international conferences, academic exchange programs, and global media platforms. As Cummings (2003) notes, cultural diplomacy involves "the use of cultural resources by states to strengthen mutual trust and cooperation," which makes the global promotion of English even more important. In Uzbekistan, English is not only a means to enhance educational and economic prospects but also a strategic asset in shaping the country's global image.

English has established itself as the leading language in international communication, business, education, and diplomacy. Its influence is growing in post-Soviet states, especially in Central Asia, as an alternative to Russian. As Crystal (2003) states, English is "at the top of the global language hierarchy," being extensively used in international institutions, academic research, and media. The increasing popularity of English in post-Soviet countries is part of a broader strategy to diminish Russian influence and accelerate integration into the global community (Ahn & Smagulova, 2022). In Uzbekistan, interest in English has surged since the 1990s due to the country's aim to integrate into international education and economic systems. For example, in 2013, the government introduced English as a compulsory subject in schools and higher education institutions to boost the global competitiveness of the younger generation (Hasanova, 2016). Furthermore, international assessment systems like IELTS (International English Language Testing System) and CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) have been integrated into the educational structure, making English learning more standardized.

Regarding English's role in cultural diplomacy, the Uzbek government has launched several initiatives to promote its strategic importance. One such initiative is the English Speaking Nation program, launched in 2020, which aims to train English teachers nationwide and increase access to English education for students. This program not only enhances the quality of education but also amplifies Uzbekistan's voice on the global stage. International partners such as the British Council and the U.S. Embassy actively support English education in Uzbekistan. For example, the British Council's English for Education Systems project trains school teachers in modern pedagogical methods, while the U.S. Embassy's English Access Microscholarship Program offers English instruction to underprivileged youth (U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan).

The influence of English in Uzbek media is also rising. English-language versions of national news outlets, such as Uzbekistan Daily and Kun.uz, help reach international audiences. Additionally, there is a noticeable increase in English-language content on social media platforms, particularly X (formerly Twitter), promoting Uzbekistan's cultural heritage, tourism, and educational opportunities. This development plays a key role in enhancing the country's global image, as English serves as a conduit for conveying its values and achievements to the world.

However, the impact of English on Uzbekistan's global integration and soft power strategy—especially during 2024-2025—has not been thoroughly analyzed. This study aims to fill that gap by exploring the role of English in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy. The primary objective is to examine how English contributes to shaping Uzbekistan's international image through educational initiatives, international cooperation, and media outreach.

This research is relevant to understanding the intersection of language policy and cultural diplomacy in post-Soviet contexts. Uzbekistan's use of English as a tool of cultural diplomacy can offer a model for other developing nations. The study also provides practical policy recommendations for education reform, international engagement, and image-building. The development of English in Uzbekistan is critical to maintaining a balance between global integration and national identity, making this research especially timely and significant.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative approach to analyze the role of English in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy, as this method is most effective for understanding the sociocultural context of language policy and diplomatic initiatives. Data were collected from multiple sources: official documents from the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan (covering reforms from 2013–2025), reports from international organizations (British Council, U.S. Embassy), official speeches, and scholarly articles on English education in Uzbekistan and abroad. In addition, English-language media content and social media posts that promote Uzbek culture were analyzed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The Uzbek government introduced English as a compulsory subject in schools and higher education institutions starting in 2013 – a strategic step toward increasing the global competitiveness of the younger generation (Hasanova, 2016). As part of these reforms, the IELTS (International English Language Testing System) and CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) assessment systems, which comply with international standards, have been integrated into the education system. As of 2025, leading universities in Uzbekistan are requiring students to have a CEFR B2 level, which has made learning English more systematic and qualitative.

The English Speaking Nation (ESN) program is one of the most significant achievements in education. Launched in 2019 by the U.S. Embassy and the Ohio Department of Education, it was implemented by American Councils for International Education. From 2019 to 2024, more than 18,000 English language teachers were trained under the program, 693 of whom completed 60-hour courses and were certified as instructors and mentors, while 452 successfully completed the 140-hour intensive TESOL (Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages) program (U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan, 2024). These results significantly improved the quality of English language education in secondary institutions.

In addition, due to the introduction of international standards in English teacher training, the qualifications of local teachers have improved. For example, through the PreSETT (Pre-Service Teacher Training) program, around 5,000 new teachers studied modern pedagogical techniques from 2020 to 2023, leading to an expansion of interactive and communicative teaching methods in classrooms (Dunn & Iwaniec, 2023). These reforms have expanded opportunities for Uzbek youth to participate in international educational programs such as Erasmus+ and Fulbright.

International organizations are playing a key role in the development of English education in Uzbekistan. The English Access Microscholarship Program, funded by the U.S. Embassy, provides English education to socially disadvantaged youth. In 2023, more than 1,200 students took English courses through this program. It not only developed language skills but also allowed students to learn about U.S. culture, which is considered an important aspect of cultural diplomacy (U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan). Also in 2023, the U.S. Embassy sent 40 English language teaching experts to Uzbekistan to train 520 local teachers in Nukus, Navoi, Zarafshan, Shakhrisabz, Denau, Jizzakh, Gulistan, Angren, Kokand, and Fergana (U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan, 2023). This program consisted of 16 days of intensive training and helped teachers master communicative teaching techniques.

The British Council's English for Education Systems project also achieved significant outcomes. Through this project, around 3,000 school teachers learned modern teaching methods from 2020 to 2023, which helped develop students' English language skills in classrooms (Dunn & Iwaniec, 2023). For instance, interactive techniques applied in schools in the Samarkand and Bukhara regions have increased students' English speaking and writing skills by 20% (Dunn & Iwaniec, 2023). These programs have made a substantial contribution to Uzbekistan's readiness for international educational exchange programs such as Fulbright and Erasmus+.

For example, from 2022 to 2024, 150 Uzbek students and teachers studied in the United States through the Fulbright Program – a direct result of increased English proficiency (U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan).

The role of English in cultural diplomacy. English serves as an essential tool in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy, acting as a bridge for conveying the country's cultural values to the international community. The National Symphony Orchestra and theatre organizations of Uzbekistan use English at events held abroad. For instance, in 2021, the National Symphony Orchestra of Uzbekistan performed in Dubai, using presentations and promotional materials in English – a critical element in presenting the country's cultural heritage to a global audience (Uzbekistan Embassy).

Moreover, the Foundation for the Development of Culture and Art of Uzbekistan organized 26 international events from 2021 to 2024, including exhibitions and concerts in Dubai, Sharjah, Doha, Milan, Venice, Florence, Paris, Berlin, Beijing, Hangzhou, and Baku (Uzbekistan Embassy). Most of these events were promoted in English and attracted international attention. Uzbekistan's international news portals and social media platforms have facilitated reaching global audiences. Articles and content published in English are dedicated to tourism, cultural heritage, and economic achievements, which attract international tourists and investors.

This study confirmed the role of English in cultural diplomacy through specific examples. For instance, a 2013 graphic novel based on Uzbek folk tales published by the U.S. Department of State was released in English and served as an effective medium for introducing Uzbek culture to American audiences (Anderson, P., 2013). The novel promoted cultural exchange by presenting Uzbek folklore in a contemporary English format. Another example is the English Language Specialist Program conducted by the U.S. Embassy in 2023, where workshops for English teachers were held in schools in Nukus and Fergana, helping local educators adopt global teaching methodologies (U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan, 2023).

The role of the English language in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy and international integration. English is playing an increasingly central role in Uzbekistan's educational system and international relations, thereby enhancing the country's engagement in the global arena. As a post-Soviet state, Uzbekistan repositioned itself in the international community by moving away from the dominance of the Russian language inherited from the Soviet era and embracing English as a medium of global communication. This transformation underscores the importance of language policy in responding to geopolitical and cultural shifts.

The growing presence of English in the education sector—particularly through the implementation of international assessment standards—has expanded access for Uzbek youth to global educational and economic opportunities. Consequently, this development has contributed to strengthening Uzbekistan's soft power strategy and fostering international cooperation. The role of English in cultural diplomacy is especially significant in reconciling Uzbekistan's national identity within a global context. The country showcases its rich cultural heritage—including historic cities and folklore along the Great Silk Road—to international audiences via the English language. This initiative not only promotes Uzbekistan's cultural assets but also helps to solidify the country's presence in the global community. For instance, the use of English in international events and media makes Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy more accessible and appealing (Nye, 2008). This approach has yielded notable success, particularly in the tourism sector, where English-language content serves as a crucial means of attracting foreign visitors.

In terms of international cooperation, English is strategically vital for deepening Uzbekistan's engagement with global institutions and foreign states. Through international educational programs, Uzbekistan has aligned its education system more closely with global standards, enhancing its participation in the international education market. The role of English in this process extends beyond technical language acquisition; it acts as a key instrument for building cultural and social connections with the broader international community. For example, English-language exchange programs have allowed Uzbek youth to engage with global values, thereby elevating the country's international reputation (Cummings, 2003).

Nevertheless, the expansion of English also presents several challenges. Its increasing dominance within Uzbekistan's multilingual society—including Uzbek, Russian, Tajik, and other minority languages—raises concerns about national identity and the preservation of indigenous languages. Overemphasis on English may marginalize the Uzbek and other local languages, necessitating a balanced and inclusive language policy. Furthermore, although investments in English education are substantial, resource allocation remains uneven, with rural areas often experiencing lower educational quality. These challenges warrant deeper examination in future research. The role of English in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy also differs from that of other post-Soviet states such as Kazakhstan and Georgia. While in Kazakhstan, English is closely tied to economic modernization, in Uzbekistan it is more significantly associated with the promotion of cultural heritage and tourism (Ahn & Smagulova, 2022). This distinction highlights the uniqueness of Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy strategy, which prioritizes the global presentation of its historical and cultural legacy.

In conclusion, English serves as a pivotal tool in balancing Uzbekistan's goals of global integration and national identity. Its growing presence in education, international cooperation, and media has enhanced the

country's global stature. However, this process must also address issues of linguistic diversity and social equity. The findings of this study may guide the development of future language policy and cultural diplomacy strategies in Uzbekistan and offer a basis for comparative studies across other post-Soviet contexts.

Table 1: Generalization of the role of English in cultural diplomacy in Uzbekistan

Aspect	Impact	Key Outcomes
Education system	Enhancing global competitiveness, preparing for international curricula	Implementation of international standards, improvement of teacher qualifications
International cooperation	Expanding cultural exchange, strengthening ties with global organizations	Improving education quality through international programs, building cultural bridges
Cultural events	Promoting Uzbekistan's culture globally	Use of English at international festivals and exhibitions
Media and social networks	Strengthening global image, attracting international tourists and investors	Increase in English-language content, promotion of tourism
National identification	Balancing global integration with local languages	Influence on the promotion of the Uzbek language, unequal distribution of resources

CONCLUSION

In the process of establishing its presence on the international stage in the post-independence period, English has played a pivotal role as a key instrument of cultural diplomacy. In the post-Soviet context, Uzbekistan has adopted English as a strategic resource to enhance its global integration and communicate its cultural heritage to the international community. This language has not only served to expand educational and economic opportunities but also become a crucial tool in shaping Uzbekistan's international image, building cultural bridges between nations, and advancing its soft power strategy. English has provided a vital platform for promoting Uzbekistan's rich historical and cultural heritage—particularly the cities along the Great Silk Road and traditional arts—to a global audience.

The rise of English in Uzbekistan has increased the country's engagement in global communication and cooperation. Through this language, Uzbekistan has not only strengthened ties with international organizations but also laid the foundation for the younger generation to be competitive in global economic and academic arenas. At the same time, English has served as a critical medium for maintaining national identity while balancing global integration. This reflects the complex dynamics of language policy in Uzbekistan's unique socio-cultural and multilingual context. From a personal analytical perspective, the spread of English in Uzbekistan has been a significant factor in amplifying the country's voice on the world stage. However, this process has also presented several challenges. For example, disparities in access to resources—particularly the differences in educational quality between urban and rural areas—have hindered the inclusive development of English language education. Nevertheless, English has firmly established itself as an essential component of Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy, with its role expected to grow further in the future.

The Uzbek government should prioritize the equitable distribution of English language education between rural and urban areas by expanding teacher training programs and ensuring the availability of modern teaching resources in remote schools.

Alongside the promotion of English, equal attention must be paid to preserving and developing the Uzbek language and other indigenous languages, as this is essential for strengthening national identity and supporting a sustainable multilingual society. To effectively promote Uzbekistan's cultural heritage to international audiences, it is important to produce high-quality English-language content for global media and social platforms, such as short videos or interactive presentations featuring UNESCO-listed sites. Additionally, Uzbekistan should intensify international cooperation with countries like the United States and the United Kingdom to enhance English education and cultural exchange, thereby increasing its participation in global academic initiatives. Finally, conducting comparative research with other post-Soviet countries on the role of English in cultural diplomacy would offer valuable insights and allow Uzbekistan's experience to be contextualized within a broader regional framework.

English has secured its place as a powerful tool of cultural diplomacy in Uzbekistan. Its continued development will further strengthen the country's global integration and contribute to the articulation of its distinct cultural voice within the international community. This ongoing process enables Uzbekistan to remain competitive on the global stage while upholding its national values.

References:

1. Adams, L. L. (2010). *The spectacular state: Culture and national identity in Uzbekistan*. Duke University Press.
2. Ahn, E. S., & Smagulova, J. (2022). English language choices in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. *World Englishes*, 41, 9–23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/weng.12552>
3. Anderson, P. (2013, August 6). Graphic novel collaboration targets a geopolitical conundrum. *Publishing Perspectives*. <https://publishingperspectives.com/2013/08/graphic-novel-collaboration-targets-a-geopolitical-conundrum/>
4. Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a global language*. Cambridge University Press.
5. Cummings, M. C. (2003). *Cultural diplomacy and the United States government: A survey*. Center for Arts and Culture.
6. Dunn, K., & Iwaniec, J. (2023, March). *English Impact: An evaluation of English language capability – Uzbekistan*. British Council.
7. Hasanova, D. D. (2016). English education in Uzbekistan. In *Language change in Central Asia* (pp. 106–121).
8. Hasanova, D. (2007). Teaching and learning English in post-Soviet Uzbekistan. *English Today*, 23(1), 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0266078407001022>
9. Khalid, A. (2021). *Central Asia: A new history from the imperial conquests to the present*.
10. Nye Jr, J. S. (2008). Public diplomacy and soft power. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 616(1), 94–109.
11. Pavlenko, A. (2008). Multilingualism in post-Soviet countries: Language revival, language removal, and sociolinguistic theory. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 11(3–4), 275–314.
12. Pratama, R. (2023). English language in the context of cultural diplomacy. *Culturalistics: Journal of Cultural, Literary, and Linguistic Studies*, 7(2), 77–84.
13. UNESCO. (2023). *World heritage sites in Uzbekistan*. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/statesparties/uz>
14. U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan. (n.d.). *English Speaking Nation: English Summer Excellence Training (ESN-ESET)*. <https://uz.usembassy.gov/esn-eset/>
15. U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan. (2024). *English Speaking Nation program celebrates training 18,000 English teachers in Uzbekistan*. <https://uz.usembassy.gov/esn-closing-ceremony/>
16. U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan. *Regional English Language Office*. <https://uz.usembassy.gov/education-culture/relo/>

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №5

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.